

CARBON CREDIT MECHANISM: GROWTH PROSPECT FOR INDIA

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Abstract

Carbon trading is a advance format, where firms or countries buy and sell carbon permits as part of a program to trim out carbon emission. It is a widespread method countries utilize in order to meet their obligations specified by international Kyoto Protocol (1997) of United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change; namely the reduction of carbon emissions in order to mitigate future climate changes. It specifically targets carbon dioxide calculated in terms of CO₂ equivalent or CO₂. People buy and sell such products because it is the most cost-effective way to achieve an overall reduction in the level of emissions, assuming that transaction costs involved in market participation are kept at reasonable levels. Problems with forest carbon arise when trees are being grown solely for their carbon. If there are other economic uses of the reforested land, such as producing fuel wood, rubber, fruits, and food crops, then the cost of carbon sequestration is lower. Communities can use carbon payments to finance sustainable tree-growing investments that produce these non-carbon benefits. Carbon Development Mechanism(CDM) is trading project which is administered by the CDM executive which reports and is accountable to the Conference of Parties(COP) Carbon Trading In India: Though India is potentially the largest market for carbon credits on the MCX, we still need to implement proper policies to allow trading of certified emission reductions (CERs), carbon credit. To increase the market for carbon trading Forward Contracts (Regulation) Amendment Bill has been introduced in the Parliament. Thus we see that Carbon Trading is definitely the “Greenest” pastures for business trading for the small and large scale private and governmental sectors in India with opportunities for everyone. So, in this paper we can review and put forward the ways and market standards that we can set so that the concept of carbon trading can have its roots in India too.

Key Words: Carbon credit, Carbon Trading, carbon permit, credit mechanism, Kyoto protocol and Carbon Trading in India

I-INTRODUCTION

India is the second largest generator of environment-friendly projects, domestic firms, public and private, are shying away from maximizing the monetary benefits derived from such carbon emission reductions. The country, which is second only to China in terms of generating of carbon credits through the introduction of low polluting technologies, ranks very low when it comes to encashing of these credits through carbon trading. Over 90 per cent of such credits generated are being held back by Indian firms, amid growing uncertainties in the global carbon trade market. As a result, there is a great opportunity awaiting India in carbon credit trading which is estimated to go up to \$100 billion by 2010. In the new regime, the country could emerge as one of the largest beneficiaries accounting for 25 per cent of the total world carbon trade, says a recent World Bank report. So, in this paper we have reviewed and put forward the concept and the growth and trend in adoption of Carbon Market in India .

Increase in GHGs mostly the Carbon dioxide is the serious problem of the era. The problem with humans contributing so much carbon dioxide is that Earth's natural system is overwhelmed and can't keep up with the rate of our CO₂ release. The natural carbon cycle is disrupted and Earth's carbon 'sinks' or places that carbon can be safely absorbed are either diminishing or saturated. The terms '**Global Warming**' and '**Climate Change**', describes what is happening..!! Global economic growth is driving higher carbon dioxide emissions and we really must manage the tremendous amounts of carbon dioxide we are emitting. Global warming has spawned a new form of commerce: the

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carbon trade. This new economic activity involves the buying and selling of “environmental services,” including the removal of greenhouse gases from the atmosphere, which are identified and purchased by eco-consulting firms and then sold to individual or corporate clients to “offset” their polluting emissions. While some NGOs and “green” businesses favor the carbon trade and view it as a win-win solution that reconciles environmental protection with economic prosperity, other environmentalists and grassroots organizations claim that it is no solution to environmental problems such as global warming.

The carbon trade is an idea that came about in response to the **Kyoto Protocol**.

KYOTO PROTOCOL

The idea came with global warming crisis, in Rio de Janeiro of Brazil, the 1992 UN Conference on the Environmental and Development clearly raised the concept of “sustainable development”. Through this conference more than 150 countries had established “United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change”, which was called UNFCCC for short.

UNFCCC is the first convention to take full control of greenhouse gas emissions including Carbon dioxide discharge, and is an international convention to fight global warming which causing a lot of and adverse effect to the development of society and economy. After that, in December 1997, the third Conference of the Parties (COP) under the UNFCCC held in Kyoto of Japan, which aimed at limiting carbon emissions in developed countries. In this way, we can curb global warming .The conference ended with an agreement of “**Kyoto Protocol**”. The Protocol took formal effect in February 16th 2005. “Kyoto Protocol” is internationally binding and enforceable agreements that will encourage countries to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The Kyoto Protocol has introduced ground breaking concepts on carbon credits, carbon footprint and emissions trading. The Kyoto Protocol is an agreement under which industrialized countries will reduce their greenhouse gas emissions between the years 2008 to 2012 to levels that are 5.2% lower than those of 1990. Several cap-and-trade systems for greenhouse gases have been implemented around the world. The most notable is the EU Emissions Trading Scheme (EU ETS), which came into effect on 1 January 2005 and is now in its second phase (2008-2012). Other countries are establishing emissions trading, and some countries such as Australia are engaging in vigorous debates about the merits of emissions trading schemes compared with other approaches. The idea behind carbon trading is quite similar to the trading of securities or commodities in a marketplace. Carbon would be given an economic value, allowing people, companies or nations to trade it. If a nation bought carbon, it would be buying the rights to burn it, and a nation selling carbon would be giving up its rights to burn it. The value of the carbon would be based on the ability of the country owning the carbon to store it or to prevent it from being released into the atmosphere. A market would be created to facilitate the buying and selling of the rights to emit greenhouse gases. The industrialized nations for which reducing emissions is a daunting task could buy the emission rights from another nation whose industries do not produce as much of these gases. The market for carbon is possible because the goal of the Kyoto Protocol is to reduce emissions as a collective. On the one hand, the idea of carbon trade seems like a win-win situation: greenhouse gas emissions may be reduced while some countries reap economic benefit. On the other hand, critics of the idea suspect that some countries will exploit the trading system and the consequences will be negative. While the proposal of carbon trade does have its merits, debate over this type of market is inevitable since it involves finding a compromise between profit, equality and ecological concerns. Carbon emissions trading is a form of emissions trading that specifically targets carbon dioxide calculated in tonnes of carbon equivalent or CO₂ and it currently constitutes the bulk of emissions trading.

Figure : Carbon Emission % in few important business countries

This form of permit trading is a common method countries utilize in order to meet the obligations specified by Kyoto Protocol; namely the reduction of the carbon emissions in an attempt to mitigate the future climate change. Emission trading works by setting a quantitative limit on emissions produced by emitters.

II- LITERATURE REVIEW

Hoeller, P. and M. Wallin (1991) : Cross-country experience suggests that in countries with high energy prices CO₂ emission intensities are low. Emission intensities differ considerably across countries as do energy prices, mainly because of large differences in taxation. Current taxes on oil products are already high in many OECD countries and represent an implicit carbon tax on oil products of over \$200 per ton of carbon in all the major European countries. The use of coal, on the other hand, is generally not taxed and in some countries is even subsidised. A reform of fossil-fuel taxation in line with carbon content would lead to major changes in the level and structure of energy taxes. For example, coal prices would probably rise sharply in many countries and it is likely that there would be price rises for gas and some oil products .**Hepburn, C. (2007)** The three Kyoto flexible mechanisms—emissions trading, the clean development mechanism (CDM), and Joint Implementation (JI)—have always been controversial. Proponents saw the mechanisms as clever tools to ensure environmental outcomes were achieved at least cost. **Birla Vivek (2012)**:Carbon credit is an umbrella term for a certificate or permit that allows an organization or a country to manufacture a fixed amount of carbon emissions which can be bartered if the full fixed allowance is not fully used. Though Carbon Credit is definitely a very lucrative proposition for both the buying and selling countries, it is the environment which pays the heaviest price, as the GHG emitting countries cause environmental degradation by polluting it.

III-OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

It is to steer companies and countries to lower their greenhouse gas emissions. Those that do not exhaust their cap are allowed to sell them in the market or to those companies in need of them. So, those who do not use up their

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entire permissible amount are rewarded by being allowed to sell their credits, while those who exceed their cap are penalized by having to pay for more credits.

- By giving a currency value to the price of polluting the atmosphere, carbon credits establish a market to reduce greenhouse emissions.
- By making carbon credits part of the manufacturing scenario, companies are forced to look at alternative and safer sources of energy.
- Participating companies save money by implementing carbon credit reduction techniques.
- Carbon credits make a positive impact on global warming because it is implemented by all countries of the world.
- Companies based in developing countries earn an extra income from this.
- It is an innovative investment avenue for people.

IV-CARBON CREDITS

The primary purpose of the Protocol was to make developed countries pay for their ways with emissions while at the same time monetarily rewarding countries with good behavior in this regard. Since developing countries can start with clean technologies, they will be rewarded by those stuck with dirty ones. This system poises to become a big machine for partially transferring wealth from wealthy, industrialized countries to poor, undeveloped countries. A CER or carbon Credit is defined as the unit related to reduction of 1 tonne of CO₂ emission from the baseline of the project activity.

Let us say that India decided to invest in a new power station, and has decided on a particular technology at the cost of X crore. An entity from an industrialized country (which could even be a company) offers to provide India with slightly better technology, which costs more (say Y crore), but will result in lower emissions. The industrialized country will only pay the incremental cost of the project – viz. Y minus X. In return, the investing country will get certified emission reductions (CERs), or credits, which it can use to meet its Kyoto commitments. This is a very good deal indeed – but for the investing country. Not only do they sell developing countries their technology, but

they also meet their Kyoto commitments without lifting a finger to reduce their domestic emissions. Countries like the US can continue to pollute at home, so long as it makes the reductions elsewhere

CARBON CREDIT MECHANISM

Kyoto Protocol worked out three mechanisms of the energy conservation and emission reduction

- Clean Development Mechanism(CDM)
- Joint Implementation (JI)
- Emissions Trade (ET)

A) Clean Development Mechanism(CDM):

Under the CDM one can cut the deal for carbon credit. Under the UNFCCC, charter any company from the developed world can tie up with a company in the developing country that is a signatory to the Kyoto Protocol. These companies in developing countries must adopt newer technologies, emitting lesser gases, and save energy. Only a portion of the total earnings of carbon credits of the company can be transferred to the company of the developed countries under CDM. There is a fixed quota on buying of credit by companies in Europe.

B) Joint Implementation (JI):

The mechanism known as “joint implementation,” defined in Article 6 of the Kyoto Protocol, allows a country with an emission reduction or limitation commitment under the Kyoto Protocol to earn emission reduction units (ERUs) from an emission-reduction or emission removal project, each equivalent to one tonne of CO₂, which can be counted towards meeting its Kyoto target. Joint implementation offers Parties a flexible and cost-efficient means of fulfilling a part of their Kyoto commitments, while the host Party benefits from foreign investment and technology transfer.

C) Emissions Trading (ET):

Parties with commitments under the Kyoto Protocol have accepted targets for limiting or reducing emissions. These targets are expressed as levels of allowed emissions, or “assigned amounts,” over the 2008-2012 commitment periods. The allowed emissions are divided into “assigned amount units” (AAUs). Emissions trading, as set out in Article 17 of the Kyoto Protocol, allows countries that have emission units to spare – emissions permitted them but not “used” - to sell this excess capacity to countries that are over their targets.

V- INDIAN SCENARIO

India comes under the third category of signatories to UNFCCC. India signed and ratified the Protocol in August, 2002 and has emerged as a world leader in reduction of greenhouse gases by adopting Clean Mechanisms (CDMs) in the past few years. According to Report on National Action Plan for operationalising Clean Development Mechanism(CDM) by Planning Commission, Govt. of India, the total CO₂-equivalent emissions in 1990 were 10, 01, 352 Gg (Gigagrams), which was approximately 3% of global emissions. If India can capture a 10% share of the global CDM market, annual CER revenues to the country could range from US\$ 10 million to 300 million (assuming that CDM is used to meet 10-50% of the global demand for GHG emission reduction of roughly 1 billion tonnes CO₂, and prices range from US\$ 3.5- 5.5 per tonne of CO₂). As the deadline for meeting the Kyoto Protocol targets draws nearer, prices can be expected to rise, as countries/companies save carbon credits to meet strict targets in the future. India is well ahead in establishing a full-fledged system in operationalising CDM, through the Designated National Authority (DNA).

India and China are likely to emerge as the biggest sellers and Europe is going to be the biggest buyers of carbon credits. Last year global carbon credit trading was estimated at \$5 billion, with India's contribution at around \$1 billion. India is one of the countries that have 'credits' for emitting less carbon. India and China have surplus credit to offer to countries that have a deficit. India has generated some 30 million carbon credits and has roughly another 140 million to push into the world market. Waste disposal units, plantation companies, chemical plants and municipal corporations can sell the carbon credits and make money. Carbon, like any other commodity, has begun to be traded on India's Multi Commodity Exchange since last the fortnight. MCX has become first exchange in Asia to trade carbon credits.

EXAMPLES OF CARBON TRADING IN INDIA

1. **Jindal Vijaynagar Steel:** Years it will be ready to sell \$225 million worth of saved carbon. This was made possible since their steel plant uses the Corex furnace technology which prevents 15 million tonnes of carbon from being discharged into the atmosphere.

2. **Powerguda in Andhra Pradesh:** The village in Andhra Pradesh was selling 147 tonnes equivalent of saved carbon dioxide credits. The company has made a claim of having saved 147 MT of CO₂. This was done by extracting bio-diesel from 4500 Pongamia trees in their village.

VI- FINDINGS

CDM POTENTIAL FOR INDIA

I) Indian Scenario- Favoring Points

- a) India - high potential of carbon credits
- b) India can capture 10% of Global CDM market
- c) Annual revenue estimated range from US\$10 million to 330 million
- d) Wide spectrum of projects with different sizes
- e) Vast technical human resource
- f) Strong industrial base
- g) Dynamic, transparent & speedy processing by Indian DNA (NCDMA) for host country approval
- h) MoU Signed between MoP and GTZ (Oct 2006)- Indo German Energy program (IGEN)

II) Sector-Wise Break-Up:

Investment done in host country approved project as on 2nd July 2007 So far, India Concentrated mainly on renewable energy (biomass, wind power, etc.) / waste heat recovery projects which generate much less CERs compared HFC23 projects.

Annual Greenhouse Gas Emissions by Sector

BENEFITS OF CARBON TRADING

1. The reduction in overall cost of meeting emission reduction targets.
2. The progressively improved definition of a "price" for carbon, particularly as the market becomes more liquid and active, and assuming that all carbon certificate products are fungible, meaning that they are equivalent ways of addressing emission reduction;
3. The opportunity to generate income from activities that previously attracted no additional revenue, such as investment in emission reduction, renewable energy generation, greenhouse friendly fuels and carbon sequestration;
4. The ability to use revenue from carbon sequestration to help fund additional planting of trees and other vegetation, for benefits such as salinity amelioration, biodiversity enhancement, conversion to greenhouse gas friendly fuels and energy, and employment and wealth creation in rural areas.

VII- CONCLUSION

There is a great opportunity awaiting India in carbon trading which is estimated to go up to \$100 billion above . In the new regime, the country could emerge as one of the largest beneficiaries accounting for 25 percent of the total world carbon trade, says a recent World Bank report. The countries like US, Germany, Japan and China are likely to be the biggest buyers of carbon credits which are beneficial for India to a great extent. The Indian market is extremely receptive to Clean Development Mechanism (CDM). Having cornered more than half of the global total in tradable certified emission reduction (CERs), India’s dominance in carbon trading under the clean development mechanism (CDM) of the Unconventional on Climate Change (UNFCCC) is beginning to influence business dynamics in the country. Various projects would create up to 306 million tradable CERs. Analysts claim if more companies absorb clean technologies, total CERs with India could touch 500 million. Of the 391 projects sanctioned, the UNFCCC has registered 114 from India, the highest for any country. India’s average annual CERs

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stand at 12.6% or 11.5 million. Hence, MSW dumping grounds can be a huge prospect for CDM projects in India. These types of projects would not only be beneficial for the Government bodies and stakeholders but also for general public.

Even though India is the largest beneficiary of carbon trading and carbon credits are traded on the MCX, it still does not have a proper policy for trading of carbons in the market. As a result the Centre has been asked by The National Commodity and Derivatives Exchange Limited (NCDEX) to put in place a proper policy framework for allowing trading of certified emission reductions (CERs), carbon credit, in the market. Also, India has huge number of carbon credits sellers but under the present Indian law, the buyers based in European market are not permitted to enter the market. To increase the market for carbon trading Forward Contracts (Regulation) Amendment Bill has been introduced in the Parliament. This amendment would also help the traders and farmers to utilize NCDEX as a platform for trading of carbon credits. However, to unleash the true potential of carbon trading in India, it is important that a special statute be created for this purpose as the Indian Contracts Act is not enough to govern the Contractual issues relating to carbon credits.

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